

Review Paper

Uncertainties in ecosystem services assessments and their implications for decision support – A semi-systematic literature review

Franziska Walther ^{a,*} , David N. Barton ^b, Jonas Schwaab ^{a,c}, Jarumi Kato-Huerta ^d, Bart Immerzeel ^b, Mihai Adamescu ^e, Erling Andersen ^f, Martha Verónica Arámbula Coyote ^g, Ildikó Arany ^h, Mario Balzan ^{g,i}, Adriana Bruggeman ^j, Claudia Carvalho-Santos ^{k,l,m}, Constantin Cazacu ^e, Davide Geneletti ^d, Relu Giuca ^e, Miguel Inácio ⁿ, Erwann Lagabrielle ^o, Sabine Lange ^p, Solen Le Clec'h ^q, Zhi Yi Vanessa Lim ^a, Ulla Mörtberg ^r, Stoyan Nedkov ^s, Ana Paula Portela ^{k,l}, Anna Porucznik ^a, Tudor Racoviceanu ^e, Paula Rendón ^t, Daniela Ribeiro ^u, Joana Seguin ^p, Mateja Šmid Hribar ^u, Vanya Stoycheva ^s, Henrik Vejre ^f, Christos Zoumides ^j, Adrienne Grêt-Regamey ^a

^a Chair of Planning of Landscape and Urban Systems (PLUS), Institute for Spatial and Landscape Development, ETH Zurich, 8093 Zurich, Switzerland

^b Norwegian Institute for Nature Research (NINA), 0855 Oslo, Norway

^c WSL Institute for Snow and Avalanche Research (SLF), 7260 Davos Dorf, Switzerland

^d Department of Civil, Environmental and Mechanical Engineering, University of Trento, 38123 Trento, Italy

^e Research Center in Systems Ecology and Sustainability, University of Bucharest, 050095 Bucharest, Romania

^f Department of Geosciences and Natural Resource Management, University of Copenhagen, 1958 Frederiksberg C, Denmark

^g Ecostack Innovations, Paola PLA3000, Malta

^h HUN-REN Centre for Ecological Research, 2163 Vácrátót, Hungary

ⁱ Institute of Applied Science, Malta College of Arts, Science and Technology (MCAST), Paola PLA9032, Malta

^j Energy, Environment and Water Research Center (EWWRC), The Cyprus Institute, 2121 Nicosia, Cyprus

^k CIBIO, Centro de Investigação em Biodiversidade e Recursos Genéticos, InBIO Laboratório Associado, Campus de Vairão, Universidade do Porto, 4485-661 Vairão, Portugal

^l BIOPOLIS Program in Genomics, Biodiversity and Land Planning, CIBIO, Campus de Vairão 4485-661 Vairão, Portugal

^m Centre of Molecular and Environmental Biology (CBMA), Minho University, 4710-057 Braga, Portugal

ⁿ Environmental Management Center, Mykolas Romeris University, 08303 Vilnius, Lithuania

^o UMR ESPACE-DEV, Université de La Réunion, 97744 Saint-Denis, La Réunion, France

^p Leibniz University Hannover, Institute of Earth System Sciences, Physical Geography and Landscape Ecology, Schneiderberg 50, 30167 Hannover, Germany

^q Earth Systems and Global Change, Wageningen University and Research, 6708PB Wageningen, the Netherlands

^r Department of Sustainable Development, Environmental Science and Engineering, KTH Royal Institute of Technology, 10044 Stockholm, Sweden

^s National Institute of Geophysics, Geodesy and Geography – Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, 1113 Sofia, Bulgaria

^t Department of Chemical and Environmental Technology (ESCET), Rey Juan Carlos University, 28933 Móstoles, Spain

^u Anton Melik Geographical Institute, Research Center of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts, 1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia

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ABSTRACT

Ecosystem services (ES) assessments are rarely integrated into decision-making processes, with uncertainties often cited as a major barrier. While various uncertainties, such as modelling and data uncertainties, are inherent in ES assessments, their role in uptake of ES assessment results in decision-making remains unclear. We conducted a semi-systematic literature review of scientific papers assessing ES to reveal how uncertainties in ES assessments relate to ES uptake, i.e., the potential use of ES assessment results by decision makers. We performed logistic regressions to analyse the influence of three main sources of uncertainty on ES uptake, i.e., (i) modelling uncertainties, (ii) uncertainties related to qualitative and quantitative descriptions of scenarios, and (iii) uncertainties related to the transfer of ES assessment results into decision-making. Furthermore, we investigated if stakeholder involvement plays a role in ES uptake. First, and most importantly, the results indicate that clarifying the policy context can decrease decision uncertainty and thus improve ES uptake. Referring to a specific policy,

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: fwalther@ethz.ch (F. Walther).

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following a decisive study purpose and documenting the intended policy entry point are factors that significantly enhance ES uptake. Second, the way how ES are modelled is related to ES uptake. Our results show that using multiple models to assess ES significantly promotes ES uptake. Third, involving stakeholders in ES assessments is significantly associated with increased documented uptake. We discuss that explicitly anchoring the assessment in a policy context increases the salience and timeliness of an ES study, assessing model uncertainties can lead to more credible results, and involving stakeholders can provide more legitimacy, which together increase the potential for ES assessments and their results to be used in decision-making. This study encourages future ES assessments to integrate uncertainties in order to support informed decision-making and promote the conservation and sustainable management of ecosystems and their services.

1. Introduction

In recent years, there has been growing recognition of the importance of ecosystem services (ES) in sustaining human well-being and the need to integrate them into decision-making processes. Global efforts are underway to conserve and sustainably manage ecosystems and the services they provide, anchored in multiple policy frameworks such as the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (GBF) (United Nations, 2022) and the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030 (EC, 2020). More specifically, the EU mandates the assessment and mapping of ES, supporting initiatives such as the UN-initiated Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (MA, 2005), the EU-wide assessment of Mapping and Assessment of Ecosystems and their Services (Maes et al., 2020) and projects such as ESMERALDA¹ and SELINA.² As a result, an increasing number of ES assessments are being published, providing scientific evidence to inform policy and decision-making (Chan and Satterfield, 2020). However, previous reviews have shown that only very few ES assessments document their actual use by decision-makers, which is also referred to as ES uptake (Barton et al., 2022; Laurans et al., 2013; Termansen et al., 2022). According to the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES), the likelihood of uptake depends on criteria such as credibility, salience, timeliness, legitimacy, and information costs (Barton et al., 2022). These criteria are influenced by multiple challenges, including lack of access to evidence for decision-makers (Cvitanovic et al., 2016; Sutherland, 2022), power dynamics such as unequal relative influence of actors and dependency between them (Jacobs et al., 2020), and the inherent uncertainties in assessing ES and translating results to decision-makers (Bertuol-Garcia et al., 2018; Polasky et al., 2015; Polasky et al., 2011). In particular, uncertainties in ES assessments and their potential implications for ES uptake have been identified as critical blind spots in current ES research (Laurans et al., 2013; Lautenbach et al., 2019; Vári et al., 2024).

Uncertainties in ES assessments can be related to various factors. The supply of, demand for and access to ES is not constant over space and time, and thus subject to considerable variability (Chan and Satterfield, 2020; Huber et al., 2013). These uncertainties are likely to be exacerbated by prediction uncertainties related to global changes, such as climate change, socio-economic trends, and the resulting alterations in land use and land cover (LULC) (Brunner and Grêt-Regamey, 2016; Elkin et al., 2013; Prestele et al., 2016). For example, climate change causes more frequent and intense weather extremes influencing ES supply, including water provision and erosion control (IPCC, 2022). Socio-economic factors, like population growth and changing consumption patterns, alter the demand for ES (Cumming et al., 2014). Other factors, such as economic disparities and land ownership, contribute to unevenly distributed access to ES (Schirpke et al., 2020). Thus, ES assessments need to incorporate the complex and uncertain ES dynamics that can occur across multiple spatio-temporal scales and vary between different groups of people (Hou et al., 2013; Mandle et al.,

2020; Martín-López et al., 2019). Moreover, recent developments in ES research point towards the necessity of acknowledging and considering the diverse values of nature (Pascual et al., 2023). These values differ depending on peoples' worldviews (Jacobs et al., 2020). Hence, the choices of representation of worldviews and knowledge systems considered within the ES assessment are likewise subject to uncertainty (Dou et al., 2023).

Technological advancements, such as remote sensing (Strith et al., 2019), along with the development of integrated ES assessment methodologies that incorporate diverse types of knowledge (Grêt-Regamey et al., 2013; Hill et al., 2020), have greatly improved our understanding of ecosystems and their services. While these improvements help reduce uncertainty, they cannot eliminate it entirely. This distinction aligns with the differentiation between epistemic uncertainty, which can be reduced with better data and models, and aleatory uncertainty, which reflects the natural variability and persists regardless of how much data is collected (Ascough et al., 2008; Maier et al., 2016). Uncertainty assessments are essential as they not only reduce some uncertainties, but also make the remaining uncertainty more explicit, ultimately enhancing the robustness and reliability of the results. Still, only a few scientific studies have assessed uncertainties in ES assessments (Hamel and Bryant, 2017; Seppelt et al., 2011). Guidance documents aimed at supporting the ES assessment process, also lack recommendations on how to deal with uncertainties (Immerzeel et al., 2023; Barton et al., 2024). Therefore, the role of uncertainties in ES assessments in terms of ES uptake remains unclear. This calls for a clearer understanding of the relationships between uncertainties and ES uptake, in order to formulate recommendations for future ES assessments.

The aim of this study is to explore how uncertainties relate to ES uptake, i.e., the potential for, or likelihood of, information from an ES assessment being considered in decision-making. To this end, we conducted a semi-systematic literature review of 904 ES assessments published in peer-reviewed scientific journals between 2018 and 2022. Based on Rounsevell et al. (2021), we distinguish between three main sources of uncertainty in ES assessments, i.e., scenario development (*scenario uncertainty*), modelling (*model uncertainty*) and the translation of the ES assessment and its findings to decision-makers (*decision uncertainty*). We then regress the various uncertainty sources against ES uptake, which is characterized by three categories: no uptake, cursory uptake, or documented uptake (Laurans et al., 2013; Barton et al. 2022). Besides unpacking the different sources of uncertainty and their relationships to ES uptake, we also investigated the role of stakeholder involvement for ES uptake. We discuss the relevance of assessing uncertainties in future ES assessments in terms of credibility, legitimacy, salience, information costs and timeliness, which together provide insight into the potential for ES uptake (Barton et al., 2022).

2. Material and methods

2.1. Conceptualisation

The semi-systematic literature review integrates the conceptual framework from the IPBES assessment on scenarios and models (IPBES, 2016) with the uncertainty framework developed by Rounsevell et al.

¹ Enhancing ecoSystem sERvices mApping for poLicy and Decision mAKing, Grant No. 642007, esmeralda-project.eu.

² Science for Evidence-based and sustainaBle decIsions about NATural capital, Grant No. 101060415, project-selina.eu.

(2021), which identifies uncertainties relevant to socio-ecological systems. By linking these frameworks, we aim to disclose key uncertainties in ES assessments and analyse how these uncertainties relate to ES uptake. Specifically, Rounsevell et al. (2021) identified three main sources of uncertainty, i.e., scenario, model, and decision uncertainty. These uncertainties can be related to three main elements of the IPBES conceptual framework (Fig. 1).

Scenario uncertainty. The IPBES conceptual framework suggests using scenarios to incorporate plausible futures and/or policy options (IPBES, 2016). Uncertainties emerge in the qualitative and quantitative descriptions of the scenarios (Rounsevell et al., 2021). The uncertainties mainly result from the limited knowledge used in scenario development due to the unpredictable nature of the future (Walker et al., 2013, Walker et al., 2003). In addition, the narratives chosen to build scenarios highly depend on the worldviews and interests involved. Incorporating the worldviews and interests of diverse stakeholders into scenario development can help to depict multiple plausible futures (Harmáčková and Vačkář, 2018). The formulation of narratives can introduce linguistic uncertainty due to multiple meanings and the vagueness of the terms used (Ascough et al., 2008; Kujala et al., 2013). Further, uncertainties go along with the translation of these narratives into quantitative metrics, also referred to as scenario parameter uncertainty (Rounsevell et al., 2021).

Model uncertainty. ES are often assessed using models (IPBES, 2016). ES assessments that do not use ES models are, for example, field observations and survey-only methods. ES models include biophysical (e.g., SWAT), economic (e.g., InVEST, cost-benefit analysis), social (e.g., participatory GIS), and integrated models (e.g., Bayesian networks or multi-criteria decision analysis) (Burkhard and Maes, 2017). Here, uncertainties exist due to the incompleteness and inaccuracy of data and models used to describe drivers, ecosystems, and ES in the assessments (Fig. 1). Limited data availability, classification errors, selection of model components, error propagation, and model assumptions are examples that contribute to model uncertainty (Rounsevell et al., 2021; Schmidt and Seppelt, 2018). To account for these uncertainties, studies argue in favour of explicit uncertainty assessment, e.g., by using sensitivity analysis, probability distributions, multiple models or other types of model validation (Bryant et al., 2018; Hooftman et al., 2022; Willcock et al., 2020).

Decision uncertainty. ES assessments provide results on the projected consequences for ES that are intended to support decision-making. Here, uncertainties arise in how ES assessments and their results are translated into decision-making, also referred to as decision uncertainty. The interpretation and application of ES research findings by decision-makers is shaped by how well the scope of the scientific study design matches the scope of a specific policy context (Barton et al., 2022; Rounsevell et al., 2021).

2.2. Literature selection

The identification, screening and inclusion phases of the literature selection are illustrated in Fig. 2. We based our search on 108,064 publications on ecosystem condition, ES or ecosystem accounting that were systematically selected from Web of Science and Scopus by Seguin et al. (2023). The database includes recent peer-reviewed studies published between 2018 and 2022 that are available in English. From the database, we performed a Boolean search on each publication’s title, abstract and keywords, requiring studies to contain at least one term related to each of the following categories: ES, quantification, uncertainty, and decision-making (as outlined in Fig. S1 and Table S1 in Supplementary Material). This resulted in the identification of 1,784 potentially relevant studies for this review. From the 1,784 studies, we identified and removed 57 duplicates, resulting in a subset of 1,727 publications (Fig. 2). In the next step, the abstracts of the subset were screened to determine whether they meet the criteria of being an application of an ES assessment (Table S4 in Supplementary Material). The screening of the abstracts resulted in the exclusion of 543 publications. Then, the full texts of the remaining publications were screened, and an additional 256 publications were excluded as they did not meet the above-mentioned criteria. In addition, 24 publications were not considered because they were not accessible. The screening process resulted in a final literature selection of 908 publications that were included in the review. The selected publications were reviewed by a group of 36 reviewers using a questionnaire. The resulting dataset contained four publications with no information on whether there was any uptake or not, which were removed. This resulted in 904 studies that were included in the data analysis. The literature review followed PRISMA guidelines (Page et al., 2021), though not all criteria were met.

Fig. 1. Inherent uncertainties in assessing ecosystem services, adaptation of the IPBES conceptual framework (IPBES, 2016) and the uncertainty framework by Rounsevell et al. (2021). Uncertainties are sourced in scenario development (scenario uncertainty), modelling (model uncertainty), and transfer of ES assessment results to policy and decision-making (decision uncertainty).”

Fig. 2. Flow diagram of literature selection, adapted from the PRISMA statement (Page et al., 2021).

Each publication was reviewed by a single reviewer, which could introduce bias. To mitigate this, we used a guidance manual, regular team meetings, and helpdesk support. We therefore classified the review as semi-systematic.

2.3. Review questionnaire

We operationalised the conceptual framework (section 2.1) by developing a questionnaire on general assessment information, scenario uncertainty, model uncertainty, decision uncertainty, stakeholder involvement, and documentation of uptake. To make sure that reviewers were aligned in their understanding of the questions, we created a guidance manual with detailed information (Table S4 in Supplementary Material). The questions and variables used in this study are outlined in Table S2 in Supplementary Material. In the following, we highlight some of the key questions used in the evaluation. We were interested in the type of scenario used (*S*), distinguishing between no scenario, exploratory scenarios, target-seeking scenarios, policy-screening scenarios, and retrospective policy scenarios or impact evaluation, according to IPBES et al. (2016). We also asked whether and what type of ES model was used (*M*) to assess model uncertainty. We adapted the categories from Walker et al. (2013), who identified different levels of uncertainty, ranging from total determinism to total ignorance, addressed by different system models. The categories to choose from in the questionnaire were whether deterministic, stochastic or several system models had been used. To describe decision uncertainty, we included questions about the consideration of the policy context within the study. Specifically, we asked about the purposes of the ES assessments (*D1*), i.e., to explore, inform, design, and decide (Barton et al., 2022; Laurans et al., 2013). In addition, we obtained information on whether the study refers to a specific policy (*D2*), covers a study area spanning across jurisdictions (*D3*), mentions transferability to other sites (*D4*), and documents the intended policy entry point of the ES assessment findings (*D5*). Furthermore, we wanted to better understand whether stakeholder involvement (*P*) influences ES uptake. Previous studies have shown that stakeholder involvement can contribute to more legitimate and reliable studies and results due to the integration of a wider range of perspectives

(Pascual et al., 2023; Weibel et al., 2018). Thus, we assessed whether the ES assessment involved stakeholders in the research process, including scenario development, data collection, modelling, and preparation of results for decision-making.

Finally, in order to assess ES uptake, we followed the typology used in Barton et al. (2022) and Laurans et al. (2013), assigning each publication to one of the following three categories: (i) no uptake, (ii) cursory uptake, or (iii) documented uptake. Studies with cursory uptake explicitly mention a potential, expected, or desired use of the ES assessment and results in decision-making. Publications categorised as documented uptake explicitly mention the implementation of the results of the ES assessment by societal actors. Documented uptake arises from studies in which the implementation of the results is demonstrated after they have been produced by researchers. Documented uptake can, for example, result from previously published reports, whose findings are taken up and documented in scientific publications. Alternatively, documented uptake can result from an experiment in which the authors gathered societal actors to discuss and convey the study results.

2.4. Data analysis

To analyse how the assessment of uncertainties relates to ES uptake, we performed two logistic regressions comparing no uptake with cursory uptake (LR I) and no uptake with documented uptake (LR II). The predictor variables were derived from the answers to the questionnaire informing about the assessment of scenario (*S*), model (*M*), and decision (*D1_{explore}*, *D1_{inform}*, *D1_{design}*, *D1_{decide}*, *D2*, *D3*, *D4*, *D5*) uncertainty, as well as stakeholder involvement (*P*). Some questions included a binary response (i.e. ES model included, yes/no) followed by a categorical choice (i.e., type of model used). The answers to these hierarchical questions were combined into single predictor variables to avoid including heavily correlated predictors (i.e. predictors at different hierarchical levels). LR I (no uptake – cursory uptake) is based on 724 complete cases, and LR II (no uptake – documented uptake) is based on 253 complete cases. Before running the regression models, we explored the correlation between the predictor variables by calculating Cramer's V (φ_c), which is suitable for estimating the association between nominal

variables (Cramér, 1946). We assessed the goodness of fit of the logistic regressions using McFadden’s pseudo R-squared statistic, which indicates the model’s ability to explain the variation in the combination of predictor variables compared to an intercept-only model (McFadden, 1974). The data analysis was carried out in R version 4.2.3 using the glm () function from the “stats” package to perform logistic regressions (R Core Team, 2023), the “pscl” package to calculate McFadden’s pseudo R-squared (Jackman, 2024), and the “vcd” package to calculate Cramer’s V (Meyer et al., 2023).

3. Results

3.1. Exploratory analysis of the semi-structured review results

We found that the majority of studies assessed regulating & maintenance ES with 740 instances, followed by provisioning ES with 619 instances and cultural ES with 522 instances (Fig. 3a). To assess these services, biophysical methods were the most commonly employed approaches, used in 500 studies (Fig. 3b). The results of the review show that only 4 % of the studies documented uptake, 67 % made a cursory reference to uptake and 29 % made no reference to uptake (Fig. 3c).

Our data revealed that scenarios were used in about one-third of all studies (n = 317) (Fig. 4a). Most of the scenarios used were exploratory (n = 195). Within the respective scenario categories, the highest documented uptake was found in studies using policy-screening or target-seeking scenarios. In contrast, the lowest shares for documented and cursory uptake were found for studies using retrospective policy scenarios or conducting an impact evaluation. Most studies used models to assess ES (n = 570). Studies without models to quantify ES had the highest share of studies without documentation of uptake. Most commonly, the ES models were deterministic with 346 instances, followed by stochastic models with 154 instances, and several system models with 70 instances (Fig. 4b). The very few studies that used

several system models showed the highest proportion of documented and cursory ES uptake. Interestingly, studies using stochastic models, describing uncertainty by probabilistic measures, had relatively low shares of documented and cursory ES uptake.

Our data also showed differences among ES studies in assessing decision uncertainty. Most studies had an exploratory (n = 672) and/or informative (n = 529) purpose (Fig. 5a). However, the highest shares of cursory and documented uptake were found in studies with the purpose to design or to decide. Nearly half of all studies considered the policy context by referring to a specific policy (n = 410) such as the EU Water Framework Directive and the EU Common Agricultural Policy. We found a similar proportion for the documentation of policy entry points (n = 351) and transferability to other sites (n = 390). Studies that considered the policy context through one of the three criteria mentioned (D2, D4, D5) showed higher shares of cursory and documented uptake (Fig. 5). Approximately 43 % of the studies had a study area that spanned across multiple jurisdictions. In addition, stakeholder involvement was part of the research process for 44 % (n = 396) of all studies (Fig. 5).

The variables shown in Figs. 4 and 5 represent the predictor variables for scenario uncertainty (S), model uncertainty (M), decision uncertainty (D), and stakeholder involvement (P), which were included in the subsequent logistic regression.

3.2. Influence of uncertainties on ecosystem services uptake

The results of the logistic regression models reveal systematic relationships between the assessment of different uncertainties and ES uptake (Fig. 6). Although Fig. 4a shows a higher share of uptake in studies that used exploratory, target-seeking or policy-screening scenarios compared to studies without scenarios, both logistic regressions showed no significant positive association of any of these scenario types with ES uptake (p > 0.05). In contrast, studies that used retrospective policy scenarios or conducted an impact evaluation were significantly

Fig. 3. Overview of studies: a. Ecosystem services types assessed (multiple categories per study possible), b. Ecosystem services methods used (multiple categories per study possible), c. Documentation of uptake.

Fig. 4. Relationships between scenario uncertainty (excluding NAs, n = 10) (a) resp. model uncertainty (excluding NAs, n = 13) (b), and uptake categories, i.e., none (red), cursory (green), documented (blue). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 5. Relationships between decision uncertainty (D1-D5) resp. stakeholder involvement (P) and uptake categories, i.e., none (red), cursory (green), documented (blue). Decision uncertainty related variables are: (D1) study purpose (excluding NAs, n = 1) with multiple categories per study possible (*To avoid overrepresenting papers with more answers, equally sized bar plots were used.); and binary variables indicating whether the study (D2) refers to a policy (excluding NAs, n = 43), (D3) stretches across jurisdictions (excluding NAs, n = 13), (D4) mentions transferability (excluding NAs, n = 36), and (D5) mentions the intended policy entry point of ES assessment results (excluding NAs, n = 57). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

negatively associated with cursory uptake. Both logistic regressions revealed significant associations between ES uptake and certain types of models used to assess ES. In particular, the use of multiple system models showed a significant positive effect on uptake compared to studies without an ES model. In addition, the use of deterministic models is also significantly associated with an increase in cursory uptake. The use of stochastic models showed no significant association with cursory or documented ES uptake. Both logistic regressions involved significant explanatory variables related to the assessment of decision uncertainty by clarifying the policy context. We found that referring to a specific policy (D2), having a decisive study purpose (D1_{decide}), and documenting the intended policy entry point (D5) were significantly positively

associated with cursory and documented ES uptake, with higher coefficients for documented uptake. Additionally, studies aiming to inform or to design were significantly associated with cursory reference to uptake. Studies that mentioned being transferable to other sites (D4) were significantly positively associated with cursory uptake. Stakeholder involvement (P) was significantly associated with higher documented uptake.

An estimate of the goodness of fit of the regression models and testing whether there is strong correlation between the predictor variables is intended to help assessing the robustness of the results. The Cramer's V correlation matrix showed no major correlations between predictor variables, suggesting that the coefficients used in both logistic

Fig. 6. Significant coefficients (p value < 0.05) describing different sources of uncertainty, i.e., scenario uncertainty (S), model uncertainty (M), decision uncertainty (D) and stakeholder involvement (P), for both logistic regressions, comparing studies of no uptake with cursory uptake (LR I) and no uptake with documented uptake (LR II). For the detailed regression table see [Table S3 in Supplementary Material](#).

regressions are not strongly affected by collinearities ([Fig. S2 in Supplementary Material](#)). The $R^2_{McFadden}$ for logistic regression I (LR I: no uptake-cursory uptake) (0.18) and logistic regression II (LR II: no uptake-documented uptake) (0.57) showed that the models have good predictive ability.

4. Discussion

We show that the scientific literature on ES assessments continues to have very limited reporting on uptake of results by decision-makers. Only 4 % of our analysed studies demonstrate documented uptake. This is in the same order of magnitude as a study by [Laurans et al. \(2013\)](#) on ES valuation, who identified a share of 2 % of studies with documented uptake, and more recently the reviews of the assessment of Nature's Contributions to People by the IPBES Values Assessment showing less than 5 % of studies documenting uptake ([Pascual et al. 2023](#); [Termansen et al. 2022](#), [Barton et al. 2022](#)). We rarely read reports on the actual uptake of ES assessment findings into policy, and our review results confirm this persistent gap between science and policy. A decade after [Laurans et al. \(2013\)](#) identified this blind spot in the ES literature, most studies still make only cursory reference to policy relevance and use.

Based on our results, we provide three main recommendations on how to assess uncertainties to enhance ES uptake. In addition, we discuss the IPBES uptake criteria and how they are linked to uncertainty assessments and ES uptake ([Barton et al., 2022](#)). Including the IPBES criteria helps to gain a better understanding of why assessing uncertainties may generally increase uptake, but not in all circumstances.

Clarifying the policy context of the ES assessment. Both logistic regressions indicate that assessing decision uncertainty by explicitly addressing the policy context ($D1_{decide}$, $D2$, $D5$) of the ES assessment study is associated with improved ES uptake. Referring to a specific policy, following a decisive study purpose and documenting the intended policy entry point are factors that are significantly positively related to ES uptake ([Fig. 6](#)). Clarifying the policy context promotes the use of appropriate spatial and temporal scales within the ES assessment. This allows for a more **timely** and **salient** study, i.e., providing results when and where they are needed, thereby promoting ES uptake ([Barton et al., 2022](#); [Lautenbach et al., 2019](#); [Rounsevell et al., 2021](#)). Importantly, ES assessment results can enter decision-making at various stages of the

policy cycle, such as agenda setting, policy formulation, implementation, or evaluation ([IPBES, 2022](#)). Our findings indicate that considering the intended entry point of the ES assessment results into the policy cycle ($D5$) is associated with improved uptake, as their relevance for decision-making can be enhanced ([Pascual et al., 2023](#); [Barton et al., 2024](#)).

Choosing appropriate models to assess ES. Our results suggest that assessing model uncertainty (M) by using multiple system models is associated with improved ES uptake ([Fig. 6](#)). Employing models with different structures to quantify ES can enhance **credibility** through improved accuracy, explicit documentation of uncertainties, and model validation ([Bryant et al., 2018](#); [Hooftman et al., 2022](#); [Willcock et al., 2018](#), [Willcock et al., 2020](#)). If the study is more credible, the potential for ES uptake increases ([Barton et al., 2022](#)). However, this finding should be treated with caution, as the associations are statistically significant, but the effect is less clear compared to other predictors, all of which represent different ways to assess uncertainty. This is reflected in the p -values, which with 0.045 (LR I) and 0.032 (LR II) do not allow such a clear rejection of the null hypothesis ([Table S3 in Supplementary Material](#)). Unlike deterministic models, statistical models allow for the integration of uncertainty through probabilistic measures ([Walker et al., 2013](#)). However, we did not observe a significant relationship between stochastic models and ES uptake. This finding indicates that while stochastic models may contribute to an improved potential for ES uptake by integrating model uncertainty through probability and thus providing more credible results, **information costs** due to the difficulty in interpreting stochastic models and their time-consuming operationalisation may outweigh the potential benefits gained from the information, which can hinder ES uptake ([Barton et al., 2022](#); [Hamel and Bryant, 2017](#); [Van Oudenhoven et al., 2018](#)). Hence, besides modelling ES, presenting results including uncertainties in an understandable and accessible manner is equally important to enable ES uptake ([Beven, 2007](#)). Therefore, when modelling ES, it is essential to choose an appropriate approach that incorporates uncertainties to enhance credibility, while also considering information costs, in order to achieve credible and feasible ES assessments.

Involving stakeholders. Our analysis suggests that the involvement of stakeholders (P) in the research process has the potential to significantly improve ES uptake ([Fig. 6](#)). Stakeholder involvement can lead to a higher **legitimacy** of ES assessments and their results, as multiple

worldviews and interests are included (Weibel et al., 2018). However, only one of our models (LR II) showed a significant association between stakeholder involvement and documented uptake, suggesting that collecting only binary information on stakeholder involvement does not provide sufficient information about implications for ES uptake (Vári et al., 2024). Studies indicate that stakeholder involvement in the study design needs to be described in more detail, e.g., which groups of stakeholders were involved in the process at which point in time, to better infer legitimacy and implications for decision-making (Bitoun et al., 2022; Isaac et al., 2023; Mandle et al., 2020; O'Connor et al., 2019). Furthermore, there are various ways to enable participation in ES assessments, such as citizen science (Schröter et al., 2017) and participatory modelling (Fagerholm et al., 2022), which consider different types of uncertainty. Thus, future ES assessment research has a lot to gain from testing how stakeholder involvement is related to the assessment of different sources of uncertainty and what implications there are for ES uptake.

Policy and decision-making processes are inherently dynamic and complex (IPBES, 2022; Pascual et al., 2023). Consequently, assessing uptake, i.e., whether ES assessment results are being considered by decision-makers, often requires the use of indirect measures or proxies, alongside a simplified representation of the decision-making process (Fig. 1). This approach, however, has limitations. In our study, we did not measure ES uptake directly. Instead, we used a documentation scheme of ES uptake originally due to Laurans et al. (2013) and developed in the IPBES Value Assessment (Barton et al., 2022), which relies on explicit mention by the authors in scientific publications. This approach may lead to an underestimation of ES uptake that occurs after publication, but is not documented in the time window covered by a single scientific paper. For example, publications over the last decade on the valuation of ecosystem services of urban trees in Oslo have contributed to integration of a module for computing regulating services in a national standard for tree valuation this year (Barton, 2023). To overcome this limitation, location-specific reviews of both scientific publications and grey literature, such as policy briefs, reports, and policy analyses, could potentially capture more instances of ES uptake and help to better understand how ES assessment results are being used in policy and decision-making. This requires a case study rather than a systematic review approach. While our study allows us to infer whether the ES assessment findings were considered within decision-making processes, it does not determine whether these findings directly influenced specific decisions or led to concrete actions, such as conservation or sustainable management initiatives. An important direction for future research would be to explore the pathways and barriers for the consideration of ES assessment results in decision-making and how these translate into actual decisions. This requires a deeper understanding of how science and policy mutually shape each other, in particular how the uncertainties highlighted in this study intersect with broader dimensions of uncertainty – such as unclear or conflicting preferences, subjective judgements, and differing ontological views – and how these factors ultimately influence decision-makers' action or inaction (Kujala et al., 2013; Slawinski et al., 2017).

5. Conclusion

Our semi-systematic literature review indicates that the uptake of ES assessment results by decision-makers remains low. To improve the potential for ES uptake, we recommend that ES assessments (i) explicitly address the policy context to produce more salient and timely findings; (ii) choose appropriate ES models that integrate uncertainty to enhance credibility while keeping information costs low; and (iii) involve relevant stakeholders throughout the research process to strengthen the legitimacy of the assessment. Although we argue that incorporating uncertainty can lead to a more salient, timely, credible, and legitimate ES assessment, factors such as reducing information costs, the type of stakeholder involvement, and power dynamics require further emphasis

in future ES research. This study encourages future ES assessments to explicitly assess uncertainties and involve stakeholders as these factors play a crucial role in the uptake of ES assessment results required for informed decision-making on the conservation and sustainable management of ecosystems and their services.

6. Declaration of generative AI in scientific writing.

During the preparation of this work the authors used DeepL Write and ChatGPT-4o in order to revise text for conciseness and conduct spell-checking. After using these tools, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Franziska Walther: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **David N. Barton:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Jonas Schwaab:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Jarumi Kato-Huerta:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Bart Immerzeel:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Investigation. **Mihai Adamescu:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Erling Andersen:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Martha Verónica Arámbula Coyote:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Ildikó Arany:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Mario Balzan:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Adriana Bruggeman:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Claudia Carvalho-Santos:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Constantin Cazacu:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Davide Geneletti:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Relu Giuca:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Miguel Inácio:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Erwann Lagabrielle:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Sabine Lange:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Solen Le Clec'h:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Zhi Yi Vanessa Lim:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Ulla Mörtberg:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Stoyan Nedkov:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Ana Paula Portela:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Anna Porucznik:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Tudor Racoviceanu:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Paula Rendón:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Daniela Ribeiro:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Joana Seguin:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Mateja Šmid Hribar:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Vanya Stoycheva:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Henrik Vejre:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Christos Zoumides:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Adrienne Grêt-Regamey:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2025.101714>.

Data availability

Data for this study are available on Zenodo at [10.5281/zenodo.14671856](https://zenodo.org/record/14671856).

References

- Ascough, J.C., Maier, H.R., Ravalico, J.K., Strudley, M.W., 2008. Future research challenges for incorporation of uncertainty in environmental and ecological decision-making. *Ecol. Model.* 219 (3–4), 383–399. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2008.07.015>.
- Barton, D.N., Immerzeel, B., Brander, L., Grêt-Regamey, A., Kato Huerta, J., Kretsch, C., Le Clech, S., Rendón Cardona, P., Seguin, J., Arámula Coyote, M.V., Babí Almenar, J., Balzan, M.V., Burkhard, B., Carvalho-Santos, C., Geneletti, D., Guisado Goñi, V., Giannakis, E., Liekens, L., Lupa, P., Ryan, G., Stepniowska, M.K., Tanács, E., van 't Hoff, V., Walther, F.E., Zoumides, C., Zwierchowska, I., Grammatikopoulou, I., Villoslada, M., 2024. Increasing uptake of ecosystem service assessments: best practice check-lists for practitioners in Europe. *One Ecosyst.* 9. <https://doi.org/10.3897/oneeco.9.e120449>.
- Barton, D.N., 2023. Value 'generalisation' in ecosystem accounting - using Bayesian networks to infer the asset value of regulating services for urban trees in Oslo. *One Ecosyst.* 8, e85021.
- Barton, D.N., Chaplin-Kramer, R., Lazos, E., Van Noordwijk, M., Engel, S., Girvan, A., Hahn, T., Leimona, B., Lele, S., Niamir, A., Özkaynak, B., Pawlowska-Mainville, A., Muradian, R., Ungar, P., Aydın, C., Iranah, P., Nelson, S., Fernández, M., Cantú, González-Jiménez, D., 2022. Chapter 4: Value expression in decision-making. In: Balvanera, P., Pascual, U., Christie, M., Baptiste, B., González-Jiménez, D. (Eds.), *Methodological Assessment Report on the Diverse Values and Valuation of Nature of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services*, IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6522261>.
- Bertuol-García, D., Morsello, C., El-Hani, C.N., Pardini, R., 2018. A conceptual framework for understanding the perspectives on the causes of the science-practice gap in ecology and conservation. *Biol. Rev.* 93, 1032–1055. <https://doi.org/10.1111/brv.12385>.
- Beven, K.J., 2007. *Environmental Modelling: an uncertain future? An introduction to techniques for uncertainty estimation in environmental prediction*. CRC Press, London, 10.1201/9781482288575.
- Bitoun, R.E., Trégarot, E., Devillers, R., 2022. Bridging theory and practice in ecosystem services mapping: A systematic review. *Environ. Syst. Dec.* 42 (1). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10669-021-09839-7>.
- Brunner, S.H., Grêt-Regamey, A., 2016. Policy strategies to foster the resilience of mountain social-ecological systems under uncertain global change. *Environ. Sci. Policy* 66, 129–139. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2016.09.003>.
- Bryant, B.P., Borsuk, M.E., Hamel, P., Oleson, K.L.L., Schulp, C.J.E., Willcock, S., 2018. Transparent and feasible uncertainty assessment adds value to applied ecosystem services modeling. *Ecosyst. Serv.* 33, 103–109. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2018.09.001>.
- Burkhard, B., Maes, J., 2017. *Mapping Ecosystem Services. Chapter 4 Ecosystem Services Quantification*. Pensoft, Sofia, pp. 92–146, 10.3897/ab.e12837.
- Chan, K.M.A., Satterfield, T., 2020. The maturation of ecosystem services: Social and policy research expands, but whither biophysically informed valuation? *People Nat.* 2 (4), 1021–1060. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pan3.10137>.
- Cvitanovic, C., McDonald, J., Hobday, A.J., 2016. From science to action: Principles for undertaking environmental research that enables knowledge exchange and evidence-based decision-making. *J. Environ. Manage.* 183, 864–874. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2016.09.038>.
- Cramér, H., 1946. *Mathematical Methods of Statistics*. Princeton University Press, Princeton, NJ.
- Cumming, G.S., Buerkert, A., Hoffmann, E.M., Schlecht, E., Von Cramon-Taubadel, S., Tschamtké, T., 2014. Implications of agricultural transitions and urbanization for ecosystem services. *Nature* 515 (7525), 50–57. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature13945>.
- Dou, Y., Zagaria, C., O'Connor, L., Thuiller, W., Verburg, P.H., 2023. Using the Nature Futures Framework as a lens for developing plural land use scenarios for Europe for 2050. *Glob. Environ. Chang.* 83, 102766. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2023.102766>.
- Elkin, C., Gutiérrez, A.G., Leuzinger, S., Manusch, C., Temperi, C., Rasche, L., Bugmann, H., 2013. A 2 °C warmer world is not safe for ecosystem services in the European Alps. *Glob. Chang. Biol.* 19 (6), 1827–1840. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.12156>.
- European Commission (EC), 2020. EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030: Bringing nature back into our lives. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52020DC0380> (Accessed 27 May 2024).
- Fagerholm, N., García-Martín, M., Torralba, M., Bieling, C., Plieninger, T., 2022. Public participation geographical information systems (PPGIS). Participatory research methods for sustainability – toolkit #1. *Gaia* 31 (1), 46–48. <https://doi.org/10.14512/gaia.31.1.10>.
- Grêt-Regamey, A., Brunner, S.H., Altwegg, J., Christen, M., Bebi, P., 2013. Integrating expert knowledge into mapping ecosystem services trade-offs for sustainable forest management. *Ecol. Soc.* 18 (3). <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-05800-180334>.
- Hamel, P., Bryant, B.P., 2017. Uncertainty assessment in ecosystem services analyses: Seven challenges and practical responses. *Ecosyst. Serv.* 24, 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2016.12.008>.
- Harmáčková, Z.V., Vackář, D., 2018. Future uncertainty in scenarios of ecosystem services provision: Linking differences among narratives and outcomes. *Ecosyst. Serv.* 33, 134–145. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2018.06.005>.
- Hill, R., Adem, Ç., Alangui, W.V., Molnár, Z., Aumeeruddy-Thomas, Y., Bridgewater, P., Tengö, M., Thaman, R., Adou Yao, C.Y., Berkes, F., Carino, J., Carneiro Da Cunha, M., Diaw, M.C., Díaz, S., Figueroa, V.E., Fisher, J., Hardison, P., Ichikawa, K., Kariuki, P., Karki, M., Lyver, P., Malmer, P.O.B., Masardule, O., Oteng Yeboah, A.A., Pacheco, D., Pataridze, T., Perez, E., Roué, M.-M., Roba, H., Rubis, J., Saito, O., Xue, D., 2020. Working with Indigenous, local and scientific knowledge in assessments of nature and nature's linkages with people. *Curr. Opin. Environ. Sustain.* 43, 8–20. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2019.12.006>.
- Hooftman, D.A.P., Bullock, J.M., Jones, L., Eigenbrod, F., Barredo, J.I., Forrest, M., Kindermann, G., Thomas, A., Willcock, S., 2022. Reducing uncertainty in ecosystem service modelling through weighted ensembles. *Ecosyst. Serv.* 53, 101398. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2021.101398>.
- Hou, Y., Burkhard, B., Müller, F., 2013. Uncertainties in landscape analysis and ecosystem service assessment. *J. Environ. Manage.* 127, 117–131. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2012.12.002>.
- Huber, R., Rigling, A., Bebi, P., Brand, F.S., Briner, S., Buttler, A., Elkin, C., Gillet, F., Grêt-Regamey, A., Hirschi, C., Lischke, H., Scholz, R.W., Seidl, R., Spiegelberger, T., Walz, A., Zimmermann, W., Bugmann, H., 2013. Sustainable land use in mountain regions under global change: synthesis across scales and disciplines. *Ecol. Soc.* 18 (3). <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-05499-180336>.
- Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES), 2016. The methodological assessment report on scenarios and models of biodiversity and ecosystem services. In: Ferrier, S., Ninan, K.N., Leadley, P., Alkamade, R., Acosta, L.A., Akçakaya, H.R., Brotons, L., Cheung, W.W.L., Christensen, V., Harhash, K.A., Kabubo-Mariara, J., Lundquist, C., Obersteiner, M., Pereira, H.M., Peterson, G., Pichs-Madruga, R., Ravindranath, N., Rondinini, C., Wintle, B.A. (Eds.), *Secretariat of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services*, Bonn, Germany.
- Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES), 2022. Summary for policymakers of the methodological assessment report on the diverse values and valuation of nature of the intergovernmental science-policy platform on biodiversity and ecosystem services. IPBES Secretariat, Bonn, Germany <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6522392>.
- Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), 2022. *Summary for Policymakers*. In: Pörtner, H.-O., Roberts, D.C., Tignor, M., Poloczanska, E.S., Mintenbeck, K., Alegría, A., Craig, M., Langsdorf, S., Löschke, S., Möller, V., Okem, A., Rama, (Eds.), *Climate Change 2022: Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability. Contribution of Working Group II to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK and New York, NY, USA, pp. 3–33 <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009325844.001>.
- Immerzeel, B., Barton, D., Brander, L., Burkhard, B., Grêt-Regamey, A., Kato Huerta, J., Kretsch, C., Le Clech, S., Rendón, P., Ryan, G., Santos Martín, F., Seguin, J., Walther, F.E., 2023. SELINA M08. Working paper on the diagnostic approach to ES models.
- Isaac, R., Albrecht, E., Felipe-Lucia, M.R., Piquer-Rodríguez, M., Winkler, K.J., Martín-López, B., 2023. Governing the co-production of nature's contributions to people: The road ahead. *Adv. Ecol. Res.* 69, 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/bbs.aacr.2023.10.001>.
- Jackman, S., 2024. *pscl: Classes and Methods for R Developed in the Political Science Computational Laboratory*. Sydney, Australia. R package version 1.5.9. <https://github.com/atahk/pscl/>.
- Jacobs, S., Zafra-Calvo, N., Gonzalez-Jimenez, D., Guibrunet, L., Benessaiah, K., Berghöfer, A., Chaves-Chaparro, J., Díaz, S., Gomez-Baggethun, E., Lele, S., Martín-López, B., Masterson, V.A., Merçon, J., Moersberger, H., Muraca, B., Norström, A., O'Farrell, P., Ordóñez, J.C., Prieur-Richard, A.-H., Rincón-Ruiz, A., Sitas, N., Subramanian, S.M., Tadesse, W., van Noordwijk, M., Pascual, U., Balvanera, P., 2020. Use your power for good: Plural valuation of nature – the Oaxaca statement. *Global Sustainab.* 3. <https://doi.org/10.1017/sus.2020.2>.
- Kujala, H., Burgman, M.A., Moilanen, A., 2013. Treatment of uncertainty in conservation under climate change. *Conserv. Lett.* 6 (2), 73–85. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1755-263X.2012.00299.x>.
- Laurans, Y., Rankovic, A., Billé, R., Pirard, R., Mermel, L., 2013. Use of ecosystem services economic valuation for decision making: Questioning a literature blindspot. *J. Environ. Manage.* 119, 208–219. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2013.01.008>.
- Lautenbach, S., Muppele, A.-C., Dormann, C.F., Lee, H., Schmidt, S., Scholte, S.S.K., Seppelt, R., Van Teeffelen, A.J.A., Verhagen, W., Volk, M., 2019. Blind spots in ecosystem services research and challenges for implementation. *Reg. Environ. Chang.* 19 (8), 2151–2172. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10113-018-1457-9>.
- Maes, J., Teller, A., Erhard, M., Conde, S., Vallecillo Rodríguez, S., Barredo Cano, J.I., Paracchini, M., Abdul Malak, D., Trombetti, M., Vigiak, O., Zuilian, G., Addamo, A., Grizzetti, B., Somma, F., Hagyo, A., Vogt, P., Polce, C., Jones, A., Marin, A., Ivtis, E., Mauri, A., Rega, C., Czucz, B., Ceccherini, G., Pisoni, E., Ceglár, A., De Palma, P., Cerrani, I., Meroni, M., Caudullo, G., Lugato, E., Vogt, J., Spinoni, J., Cammalleri, C.,

- Bastrup-Birk, A., San-Miguel-Ayanz, J., San Román, S., Kristensen, P., Christiansen, T., Zal, N., De Roo, A., De Jesus Cardoso, A., Pistocchi, A., Del Barrio Alvarez, I., Tsiamis, K., Gervasin, E., Deriu, I., La Notte, A., Abad Viñas, R., Vizzarri, M., Camia, A., Robert, N., Kakoulaki, G., Garcia Bendito, E., Panagos, P., Ballabio, C., Scarpa, S., Montanarella, L., Orgiazzi, A., Fernandez Ugalde, O., Santos-Martín, F., 2020. Mapping and Assessment of Ecosystems and their Services: An EU ecosystem assessment, EUR 30161 EN. Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg.
- Maier, H.R., Guillaume, J.H.A., Van Delden, H., Riddell, G.A., Haasnoot, M., Kwakkel, J. H., 2016. An uncertain future, deep uncertainty, scenarios, robustness and adaptation: How do they fit together? *Environ. Model. Softw.* 81, 154–164. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2016.03.014>.
- Mandle, L., Shields-Estrada, A., Chaplin-Kramer, R., Mitchell, M.G.E., Bremer, L.L., Gourevitch, J.D., Hawthorne, P., Johnson, J.A., Robinson, B.E., Smith, J.R., Sonter, L.J., Verutes, G.M., Vogl, A.L., Daily, G.C., Ricketts, T.H., 2020. Increasing decision relevance of ecosystem service science. *Nat. Sustainab.* 4 (2), 161–169. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-020-00625-y>.
- Martín-López, B., Felipe-Lucia, M.R., Bennett, E.M., Norström, A., Peterson, G., Plieninger, T., Hicks, C.C., Turkelboom, F., García-Llorente, M., Jacobs, S., Lavorel, S., Locatelli, B., 2019. A novel telecoupling framework to assess social relations across spatial scales for ecosystem services research. *J. Environ. Manage.* 241, 251–263. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2019.04.029>.
- McFadden, D., 1974. Conditional logit analysis of qualitative choice behavior. In: Zarembka, P. (Ed.), *Frontiers in Econometrics*. Academic Press, pp. 105–142.
- Meyer, D., Zeileis, A., Hornik, K., Friendly, M., 2023. vcd: Visualizing Categorical Data. R package version 1.4-12, <<https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=vcd>>.
- Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (MA), 2005. *Ecosystems and human well-being: Synthesis*. Island Press, Washington, DC.
- O'Connor, R.A., Nel, J.L., Roux, D.J., Lim-Camacho, L., Van Kerkhoff, L., Leach, J., 2019. Principles for evaluating knowledge co-production in natural resource management: Incorporating decision-maker values. *J. Environ. Manage.* 249. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2019.109392>.
- Page, M.J., McKenzie, J.E., Bossuyt, P.M., Boutron, I., Hoffmann, T.C., Mulrow, C.D., Shamseer, L., Tetzlaff, J.M., Akl, E.A., Brennan, S.E., Chou, R., Glanville, J., Grimshaw, J.M., Hróbjartsson, A., Lahu, M.M., Li, T., Loder, E.W., Mayo-Wilson, E., McDonald, S., McGuinness, L.A., Stewart, L.A., Thomas, J., Tricco, A.C., Welch, V.A., Whiting, P., Moher, D., 2021. The PRISMA 2020 statement: An updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ*. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n71>.
- Pascual, U., Balvanera, P., Anderson, C.B., Chaplin-Kramer, R., Christie, M., González-Jiménez, D., Martín, A., Raymond, C.M., Termansen, M., Vatn, A., Athayde, S., Baptiste, B., Barton, D.N., Jacobs, S., Kelemen, E., Kumar, R., Lazos, E., Mwampamba, T.H., Nakangu, B., O'Farrell, P., Subramanian, S.M., van Noordwijk, M., Ahn, S., Amaruzumam, S., Amin, A.M., Arias-Arrevalo, P., Arroyo-Robles, G., Cantú-Fernández, M., Castro, A.J., Contreras, V., de Vos, A., Dendoncker, N., Engel, S., Eser, U., Faith, D.P., Filyushkina, A., Ghazi, H., Gómez-Baggethun, E., Gould, R.K., Guirunet, L., Gundimeda, H., Hahn, T., Harmáčková, Z. V., Hernández-Blanco, M., Horcea-Milcu, A.-I., Huambachano, M., Wicher, L.H., Ískender Aydın, C.N., Islar, M., Koessler, A.-K., Kenter, J.P., Kosmus, M., Lee, H., Leimona, B., Lele, S., Lenzi, D., Lliso, B., Mannetti, L.M., Merçon, J., Monroy-Sais, A. S., Mukherjee, N., Muraca, B., Muradian, R., Murali, R., Nelson, S.H., Némogá-Soto, G.R., Nguhohou-Poufoun, J., Niamir, A., Nuesiri, E., Nyumba, T.O., Özkaynak, B., Palomo, I., Pandit, R., Pawłowska-Mainville, A., Porter-Bolland, L., Quaas, M., Rode, J., Rozzi, R., Sachdeva, S., Samakov, A., Schaafsma, M., Sitas, N., Ungar, P., Yiu, E., Yoshida, Y., Zent, E., 2023. Diverse values of nature for sustainability. *Nature* 620, 813–823. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-023-06406-9>.
- Polasky, S., Carpenter, S.R., Folke, C., Keeler, B., 2011. Decision-making under great uncertainty: Environmental management in an era of global change. *Trends Ecol. Evol.* 26 (8), 398–404. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2011.04.007>.
- Polasky, S., Tallis, H., Reyers, B., 2015. Setting the bar: Standards for ecosystem services. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* 112 (24), 7356–7361. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1406490112>.
- Prestele, R., Alexander, P., Rounsevell, M.D.A., Arneth, A., Calvin, K., Doelman, J., Eitelberg, D.A., Engström, K., Fujimori, S., Hasegawa, T., Halvik, P., Humpenöder, F., Jain, A.K., Kristin, T., Kyle, P., Meiyappan, P., Popp, A., Sands, R. D., Schaldach, R., Schüngel, J., Stehfest, E., Tabeau, A., van Meijl, J., Verburg, P.H., 2016. Hotspots of uncertainty in land-use and land-cover change projections: a global-scale model comparison. *Global Change Biol.* 22, 3967–3983. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.13337>.
- R Core Team, 2023. R: A language and environment for statistical computing. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria (version 4.2.3). <https://www.R-project.org/>.
- Rounsevell, M.D.A., Arneth, A., Brown, C., Cheung, W.W.L., Gimenez, O., Holman, I., Leadley, P., Luján, C., Mahevas, S., Maréchal, I., Péliissier, R., Verburg, P.H., Vieilledent, G., Wintle, B.A., Shin, Y.-J., 2021. Identifying uncertainties in scenarios and models of socio-ecological systems in support of decision-making. *One Earth* 4 (7), 967–985. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2021.06.003>.
- Schirpke, U., Scolozzi, R., Dean, G., Haller, A., Jäger, H., Kister, J., Kovács, B., Sarmiento, F.O., Sattler, B., Schleyer, C., 2020. Cultural ecosystem services in mountain regions: Conceptualising conflicts among users and limitations of use. *Ecosyst. Serv.* 46, 101210. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2020.101210>.
- Schmidt, S., Seppelt, R., 2018. Information content of global ecosystem service databases and their suitability for decision advice. *Ecosyst. Serv.* 32, 22–40. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2018.05.007>.
- Schröter, M., Kraemer, R., Mantel, M., Kabisch, N., Hecker, S., Richter, A., Neumeier, V., Bonn, A., 2017. Citizen science for assessing ecosystem services: Status, challenges and opportunities. *Ecosyst. Serv.* 28, 80–94. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2017.09.017>.
- Seguin, J., Lange, S., Rendón, P., Barton, D. N., Immerzeel, B., Grêt-Regamey, A., Roche, P., Thomas, I. N., 2023. Report: Development of the SELINA Super-Query.
- Seppelt, R., Dormann, C.F., Eppink, F.V., Lautenbach, S., Schmidt, S., 2011. A quantitative review of ecosystem service studies: Approaches, shortcomings and the road ahead: Priorities for ecosystem service studies. *J. Appl. Ecol.* 48 (3), 630–636. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2664.2010.01952.x>.
- Slawinski, N., Pinkse, J., Busch, T., Banerjee, S.B., 2017. The role of short-termism and uncertainty avoidance in organizational inaction on climate change: A multi-level framework. *Bus. Soc.* 56 (2), 253–282. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0007650315576136>.
- Strith, A., Bebi, P., Grêt-Regamey, A., 2019. Quantifying uncertainties in earth observation-based ecosystem service assessments. *Environ. Model. Softw.* 111, 300–310. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2018.09.005>.
- Sutherland, W.J., 2022. 1. Introduction: The Evidence Crisis and the Evidence Revolution. In: Sutherland, W.J. (Ed.), *Transforming Conservation: A practical Guide to Evidence and Decision-Making*. UK: Open Book Publishers, Cambridge, pp. 3–28. <https://doi.org/10.11647/OBP.0321.01>.
- Termansen, M., Jacobs, S., Mwampamba, T.H., Ahn, S., Castro, A., Dendoncker, N., Ghazi, H., Gundimeda, H., Huambachano, M., Lee, H., Mukherjee, N., Némogá, G.R., Palomo, I., Pandit, R., Schaafsma, M., Nguhohou, J., Choi, A., Filyushkina, A., Hernández-Blanco, M., Contreras, V., González-Jiménez, D., 2022. Chapter 3: The potential of valuation. In: Balvanera, P., Pascual, U., Christie, M., Baptiste, B., González-Jiménez, D. (Eds.), *Methodological Assessment Report on the Diverse Values and Valuation of Nature of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services*. IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6521298>.
- United Nations, Convention on Biological Diversity, 2022. Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework. 15/4. <https://www.cbd.int/doc/decisions/cop-15/cop-15-dec-04-en.pdf> (Accessed 27 May 2024).
- Van Oudenhoven, A.P.E., Schröter, M., Drakou, E.G., Geijzendorffer, I.R., Jacobs, S., Van Bodegom, P.M., Chazee, L., Czúcz, B., Grunewald, K., Lillebø, A.I., Mononen, L., Nogueira, A.J.A., Pacheco-Romero, M., Perennou, C., Remme, R.P., Rova, S., Syrbe, R.-U., Tratalos, J.A., Vallejos, M., Albert, C., 2018. Key criteria for developing ecosystem service indicators to inform decision making. *Ecol. Ind.* 95, 417–426. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2018.06.020>.
- Vári, A., Adamescu, C.M., Balzan, M., Gocheva, K., Götzl, M., Grunewald, K., Inácio, M., Linder, M., Obiang-Ndong, G., Pereira, P., Santos-Martin, F., Sieber, I., Stepienwska, M., Tanács, E., Termansen, M., Tromeur, E., Vačkárová, D., Czúcz, B., 2024. National mapping and assessment of ecosystem services projects in Europe – Participants' experiences, state of the art and lessons learned. *Ecosyst. Serv.* 65, 101592. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2023.101592>.
- Walker, W.E., Harremoës, P., Rotmans, J., Van Der Sluijs, J.P., Van Asselt, M.B.A., Janssen, P., Krayer Von Krauss, M.P., 2003. Defining uncertainty: A conceptual basis for uncertainty management in model-based decision support. *Integr. Assess.* 4 (1), 5–17. <https://doi.org/10.1076/iaij.4.1.5.16466>.
- Walker, W.E., Lempert, R.J., Kwakkel, J.H., 2013. *Deep Uncertainty*. In: Gass, S.I., Fu, M. C. (Eds.), *Encyclopedia of Operations Research and Management Science*. Springer, Boston, MA. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4419-1153-7_1140.
- Weibel, B., Babe, S.-E., Burkhard, B., Grêt-Regamey, A., 2018. On the importance of a broad stakeholder network for developing a credible, salient and legitimate tiered approach for assessing ecosystem services. *One Ecosyst.* 3, e25470. <https://doi.org/10.3897/oneeco.3.e25470>.
- Willcock, S., Hooftman, D.A.P., Blanchard, R., Dawson, T.P., Hickler, T., Lindeskog, M., Martínez-López, J., Reyers, B., Watts, S.M., Eigenbrod, F., Bullock, J.M., 2020. Ensembles of ecosystem service models can improve accuracy and indicate uncertainty. *Sci. Total Environ.* 747. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.141006>.
- Willcock, S., Martínez-López, J., Hooftman, D.A.P., Bagstad, K.J., Balbi, S., Marz, A., Prato, C., Sciandrello, S., Signorello, G., Voigt, B., Villa, F., Bullock, J.M., Athanasiadis, I.N., 2018. Machine learning for ecosystem services. *Ecosyst. Serv.* 33, 165–174. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2018.04.004>.